

The contribution of future orientation towards employability in students of vocational high school

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ABSTRACT

The employability of students in vocational high schools is a major concern that must be considered. Employability as the ability and skills that will make it easier for individuals to get a job. Future orientation is one of the factors that can affect employability. This study aims to test the role of future orientation on student employability empirically. The population in this study were all students of class XII at Vocational High School Piri 1 Yogyakarta, totaling 150 students. The sample in this study amounted to 58 students and selected using cluster random sampling techniques. The research method used is a quantitative method with a scale of employability and a scale of future orientation. Analysis of the data used in this study is the product-moment analysis technique. The results of data analysis showed that there was a very significant positive correlation between future orientation towards employability with $r = 0.636$ and significance level $(p) = 0.000$ ($p < 0.01$). Future orientation contributes 40.5% to employability, and the remaining 59.5% is influenced by other variables.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Individuals need to prepare themselves as much as possible in an effort to face the competitive world of the job market [1]. Employability is one of the skills that need to be possessed and developed to face this competition [2]. Furthermore, in vocational education, employability is the primary concern that needs to be considered [3], because it is a provision that will facilitate individuals to find work in the future [4]. The impact of the availability of employability on individuals is that individuals are able to manage their careers more optimally [5, 6]. Developing and increasing employability in students is very important [7] because it can improve teamwork, communication, self-management, analysis, and critical thinking skills [8].

Employability plays an important role in planning professional development and effective career advancement in individuals, and with strong employability, individuals can realize career goals and start entrepreneurship or work [4]. The impact of low employability is low self-confidence, lack of effort, and willingness to enter the workforce [9]. Individuals with low employability tend to be more difficult to enter the workforce or get a job in accordance with the expected career [10]. In addition, a large number of unemployment today is also caused by low employability [11]. Other negative impacts caused by low employability are inappropriate decision making, conflict, inappropriate leadership, low meta-cognitive skills, ineffective performance, low social responsibility, and pessimism [12].

Employability is the constant ability of individuals to do, to get, or to create work [13, 14]. It also refers to the ability of individuals to enter the workforce, adapts to the workplace, and be dynamic in the workplace [15, 16]. Employability is a skill, knowledge, and competency that can improve an individual's ability to get a job and to enter the job market more easily [17]. Employability is a set of skills, knowledge, and personal attributes that make an individual more likely to find work and succeed in his career field [18]. Employability is defined as a form of skill from special abilities that enable individuals to identify and realize career opportunities [19].

Fugate and Ashforth [19] provide the concept of employability dimensions. These dimensions consist of Career identity, personal adaptability, and social and human capital. Employability is the combined result of the dimensions of career identity, personal adaptability, and social and human capital so that these dimensions are considered collectively. Each of these dimensions combines to produce an employability concept. Career Identity is a representation of self-identity in the workplace that brings together a variety of career experiences and aspirations. These include goals, hopes, and fears; personality traits; values, beliefs and norms, interaction style, and so on. Career identity is similar to construction, such as role identity, job identity, and organizational identity that portrays a person at a particular job.

Personal Adaptability is the ability of individuals to change personal factors in themselves to adapt to the demands of the workforce. Individuals who have meaningful personal adaptability have the abilities needed to adapt to their work and the abilities needed to identify and realize opportunities for getting a job. The skills contained in these abilities consist of several skills, namely: confidence in adapting, a tendency to learn, openness, confidence in self-control, and self-efficacy. Social and human capital is the ability of individuals to identify and realize employment opportunities that are strongly influenced by social and human capital. Social and human capital is good intentions inherent in social networks. Individuals with social and human capital can find work by utilizing social networks or through informal relationships and also formal networks.

There are many factors that increase individual employability, one of which is future orientation [20]. The concept of future orientation is related to employability. It works like a map that will induce individuals in a career or work [21]. This orientation provides individuals with facilities for job choices and career planning, which in turn will have an impact on their ability to adapt [22]. The higher the level of future orientation that an individual has, the lower the level of career doubt he/she has in the future [23]. Future orientation is also a psychological resource that gives individuals positive beliefs and hopes for the success of their careers [24].

Future orientation is defined as the ability to interpret changes in the environment as an effort to ensure long-term survival and success [25]. Future orientation is the ability of individuals to predict and anticipate several possibilities as an effort to organize and plan for their future [26]. It refers to the extent to which individuals are involved in future investment planning, even though they must postpone their current satisfaction [27]. Future orientation is an individual's tendency to connect his current choices with further goals [28]. It is also defined as an image that an individual has about his future, and as a foundation or reference for building it [29].

Aspects of future orientation, according to Nurmi [30] include motivation, planning, and evaluation. Each of these aspects combines to produce a concept of future orientation. Motivation is the beginning of forming an individual's future orientation, which includes motives, interests, and goals. Motivation can help individuals to make their interests more specific and assist individuals in designing more realistic goals. Motivation in future orientation is a process that involves several stages. First, the emergence of new knowledge that is relevant to individual motives. Second, individuals begin to explore knowledge related to new interests. Third, determine the goals that ultimately decide the readiness to make commitments that contain the objectives.

Planning is how individuals make plans to realize their interests and goals. Planning applied to future orientation can be done by: first, individuals make a picture of the goals to be realized. Second, individuals make plans to realize their goals. Look for and determine ways to realize these goals by seeing whether the objectives set in accordance with the real conditions faced or not and prepare various strategies when meeting conditions that do not support the realization of the goals. Finally, the implementation of plans and strategies that have been made individually. Evaluation is the end of forming a future orientation. Evaluation is an individual's evaluation of the possibility of achieving a goal. Evaluation involves causal attributes based on the individual's appreciation of the successes and failures experienced, thereby affecting the expectations and beliefs of individuals regarding the possibility of achieving these goals. The results of this evaluation will be feedback on the goals set to strengthen or weaken the individual's goals. This study aimed to examine future orientation's role in predicting the employability of students at Vocational High School Piri 1 Yogyakarta empirically.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Participant

The population in this study were all students of class XII at Vocational High School Piri 1 Yogyakarta, totaling 150 students. The sample is part of the population, so it must have the characteristics possessed by the population. The sampling technique used in this study is a cluster random sampling technique. A cluster random sampling technique is a sampling technique used if randomization is done on groups, not on individual subjects.

Participants in this study are 58 grade XII students of Vocational High School Piri 1 Yogyakarta. The participants are students of 5 different majors, namely: light vehicle engineering, motorcycle engineering, machinery engineering, audio-video engineering, and electrical power installation engineering. The selection of subjects was randomized using a cluster random sampling technique.

2.2. Instruments

The data in this study are collected with scales as research instruments. The scale of employability is based on the dimension of employability, according to Fugate, Kinicki, and Ashforth [31], namely: career identity, personal adaptability, and social and human capital. The scaling model used for the scale of employability is the Likert scale model. Examples of employability scale items are: "I feel that the practice of fieldwork can increase knowledge and abilities about work", "I hope to find work that suits my field", and "I feel schools in Vocational High Schools can help prepare myself for work".

The scale of future orientation is adapted from the aspects of future orientation, according to Nurmi [30], namely: motivation, planning, and evaluation. The scaling model used for future orientation scales is the Likert scale model. Examples of future orientation scale items are: "I already have information about the work I will choose in the future", "I want to have a job that is in line with my future goals", and "Hard determination can realize the work I want in the future".

2.3. Validity and reliability of instruments

Validity has the accuracy of a measurement instrument in carrying out its measurement function. A measuring instrument has high validity if the measuring instrument can produce precise and accurate results. Reliability is an instrument that can be trusted to be used as a data collection tool because the instrument is already good. Measuring instruments are said to be reliable if the measurement results obtained do not change, which is done at different times.

The trial analysis of 42 subjects on the scale of employability obtained the results of the reliability coefficient (α) of 0.896 with a range of different power index items (corrected item-total correlation) that move from 0.355 to 0.691. Valid and reliable items that will be used for research are 24 items. The results of the trial analysis of 42 subjects on the scale of future orientation obtained the results of the reliability coefficient (α) of 0.876 with a range of different power index (corrected item-total correlation) that moves from 0.326 to 0.632. Valid and reliable items that will be used for research are 18 items.

2.4. Data analysis

The method for analyzing data is parametric statistical methods. Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS 19.0 for windows, through the Product-moment analysis which is a statistical analysis technique to determine the role of future orientation towards employability.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Prerequisite test

3.1.1. Normality test

Based on the results of the normality test analysis listed in Table 1, it is known that the significance value of the employability and future orientation variables are 0.197 and 0.197, which have $p > 0.05$. It means that each data is normally distributed, so it can be concluded that each variable has a distribution of normally distributed data.

Table 1. Distribution normality test

Variable	Score K-SZ	Significance	Explanation
Employability	0.103	0.197	Normal
Future orientation	0.103	0.197	Normal

3.1.2. Linearity test

Linearity test results between future orientation to employability shown in Table 2 obtained F linearity of 44.003 with a significance level (p) of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), which means linear or there is a line connecting the future orientation variables to employability.

Table 2. Linearity test

Variable	F Linearity	Significance	Explanation
Future orientation to employability	44.003	0.000	Linear

3.2. Hypothesis test

Table 3 shows that the future orientation of students has a very significant positive correlation to the employability of students at Vocational High School Piri 1 Yogyakarta. These results indicate that the proposed hypothesis is accepted so that the employability variable can be predicted based on future orientation. The results of this study are in line with several previous studies that found that future orientation plays an important role in increasing employability [32]. Future orientation contributes 40.5% to employability, and the remaining 59.5% can be influenced by other variables. Factors that influence future orientation include soft-skill factors, problem-solving skill factors, internship experience factors, special skills factors, and learning achievement factors [33]. Some researchers add other factors that affect employability include learning achievement, self-concept [34], learning motivation and social support [35], career management practices, work experience, training, and education [36].

Table 3. Product moment correlation coefficient

Variable	R Square	r	Significance	Rule	Explanation
Future orientation to employability	0.405	0.636	0.000	$P < 0.01$	There's a very significant correlation

Some researchers find that future orientation plays a direct or indirect role in the level of employability [37]. Future orientation helps individuals in the decision-making process effectively. Decision-making ability is essential in employability because this process is related to the vision of a career of individuals in the future [38, 39]. Individual representations about the future are very helpful in developing career choices and positive attitudes into the world of work. Future-oriented individuals can anticipate disruptive events and predict the final results they will get later, thus making themselves optimistic about getting a job [40]. In addition, individuals will view the future as opportunities that are open to their careers [41].

Future orientation can be a source of motivation for individuals to get a job because future orientation provides direction for individuals to develop plans or strategies that make it easier to enter the workforce [42, 43]. The results of several researchers indicate that future orientation is positively related to work readiness and individual career outcomes [44], such as career exploration and career planning [32]. It also contributes positively to the formation of vocational interest, which is an important part of an individual's career identity [45]. Future-oriented individuals are shown with the characteristics of planning, perseverance, responsibility, and awareness, tend to experience more active interest, followed by social interest and investigation, where it is part of the attributes of employability [40].

This research can provide insight into work readiness for Vocational High School students, especially twelfth-grade students. The findings in this study indicate that future orientation plays an active role in determining direction, planning strategies, and career decisions. Individuals with future orientation tend to have higher employability because they already know what to be prepared to enter the workforce or entrepreneurship. The results of this study can also be useful for teachers. In addition to teaching vocational skills, teachers are also responsible for guiding and directing their students in planning for their future careers in accordance with the potential vocational skills of students. Students can ask for various suggestions related to their careers that need to be prepared in the future. It is hoped that students are more ready to enter the workforce and know the direction of his career.

4. CONCLUSION

Future orientation has a contribution to the employability of students' Vocational High School Piri 1 Yogyakarta. Students who have a good future orientation are shown by students who have high motivation,

students have plans and strategies that are right on target and are able to evaluate everything that has been done. The level of future orientation owned by students can determine the level of employability. Future orientation contributes 40.5% to employability, and the remaining 59.5% is influenced by other variables.

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